

2º filtro de seleção

Base: IEEE

Total de artigos: 7

Artigos incluídos: 5 (CI1=5, CI2=0)

Artigos excluídos: 2 (CE1=2, CE2=0, CE3=0, CE4=0, CE5=0, CE6=0)

ID	Título	Link	Resumo	CI	CE	Motivo da exclusão
001	Desarrollo de un PACS usando código abierto bajo estándar DICOM	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/6868587	The Provincial Health System (Sistema Provincial de Salud, SIPROSA) divides Tucumán in four programmatic areas, where there are public hospitals and Health Primary Attention Centers (Centros de Atención Primaria de Salud, CAPS). The purpose of this structure is to regulate the health care assistance allowing the access to all population. Since 2005 the SIPROSA joined a modernization program of the provincial government computerizing the main hospitals. In this regard, it has been working for almost two years in the implementation of a Computerized Medical Record System. Thus, all patient care information will be dumped in the same public health database. Thereby, through this process it will be possible to access the patient clinical record, medical history, Rx images, medication, programs involved, among other details. To manage digital Medical Imaging in health centers in order to storage, transmit and display medical images, PACS (Picture Archiving and Communication System) are used. But they are expensive and very difficult to be incorporated in low-resource institutions. In this context, the aim of this work is to develop a DICOMizing PACS, under the DICOM standard, using free software . It was performed a technology assessment to evaluate the software available, network implementation (WLAN, LAN, WADO) in different scenarios, the security of information and new technologies.	CI1		
002	Enabling the first step for IoT health systems using Antidote and IEEE 11073	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8369020	The increasing cost of healthcare, the desire of keeping a high-quality life in face of chronic conditions, and the increasing availability of personal health devices (PHDs) are the ingredients of “IoT health” vision. In parallel, a growing number of consumer electronic (CE) devices like TVs, refrigerators or media players are becoming capable of taking the role of “health hub”, that is, a data collector for the sensor PHDs. Many PHDs (and the respective collectors) follow a standard protocol stack for health devices: IEEE 11073-20601. This paper presents Antidote: a portable, open-source implementation of the IEEE 11073-20601 stack, which further promotes this standard and increases its availability to the developer community. One of the main contributions of Antidote is how it exports health data using a DataList XML or JSON format, which helps its integration by developers in different platforms. Finally, it is presented our experience using Antidote on different scenarios, such as on mobile platforms and IoT networks	CI1		
003	Classification of Cardiac Abnormalities From ECG Signals Using SE-ResNet	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9344255	In PhysioNet/Computing in Cardiology Challenge 2020, we developed an ensemble model based on SE-ResNet to classify cardiac abnormalities from 12-lead electrocardiogram (ECG) signals. We employed two residual neural network modules with squeeze-and-excitation blocks to learn from the first 10-second and 30-second segments of the signals. We used external open-source data for validation and fine-tuning during the model development phase. We designed a multi-label loss to emphasize the impact of wrong predictions during training. We built a rule-based bradycardia model based on clinical knowledge to correct the output. All these efforts helped us to achieve a robust classification performance. Our final model achieved a challenge validation score of 0.682 and a full test score of 0.514, placing our team HeartBeats 3rd out of 41 in the official ranking. We believed that our model has a great potential to be applied in the actual clinical practice, and planned to further extend the research after the challenge.		CE1	O sistema não é de código-aberto. Utiliza apenas dados abertos para validação.

004	Design and development of a customizable telemedicine platform for improving access to healthcare for underserved populations	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8037404	Telemedicine offers a method to bridge the healthcare access gap in low and middle income countries (LMICs) by connecting providers with patients using appropriate technology. Here we describe the design and development of a novel modular telemedicine platform, Intelhealth, that would enable health systems to connect remote doctors with patients in rural clinics using a customizable Android-based platform and a cloud-based electronic health record system at the backend (OpenMRS). This open source platform enables task shifting of medically relevant information gathering by a local health worker, transmission of this information to a remote doctor, and a telephonic conversation between the doctor and the patient that subsequently allows for delivery of an appropriate therapeutic plan. Intelhealth is designed to operate on a low bandwidth internet environment, and will be tested and validated in rural health clinics in India.	CI1		
005	A scalable mHealth system for noncommunicable disease management	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/6970259	Barriers to effective screening and management of NCDs in resource-constrained regions include limited availability of trained personnel, access to affordable automatic medical devices, and longitudinal clinical data. We present an end-to-end mHealth system which takes advantage of the almost universal availability of smartphones in order to address these barriers in a scalable and affordable manner. Our system includes simple, low-cost (5–20) and open-source peripherals that allow a minimally trained person to collect high-quality medical data at the point-of-care through a standard smartphone; allows the reliable transmission of clinical data even in the case of high-latency network connections; stores data in a cloud-based system, making patient records accessible anywhere; and enables both crowdsourced diagnostics and generation of annotated data for the research and development of automatic decision support and risk assessment systems. We show examples of the different elements of the system tailored for the management of cardiovascular disease and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, which includes prototypes of the low-cost peripherals. In a validation study (of 40 volunteers), our smartphone-based blood pressure (BP) monitor was shown to measure BP, heart rate and respiration rate with a mean-absolute-error of less than 5 units from the reference values for 80% of the measurements.	CI1		
006	mHealth4Afrika Beta v1 Validation in Rural and Deep Rural Clinics in Ethiopia, Kenya, Malawi and South Africa	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8601681	mHealth4Afrika is a collaborative research and innovation project, focused on supporting Horizon 2020 Societal challenges and Sustainable Development Goal 3. It is researching and evaluating the potential impact of co-designing and developing an open source, multilingual enabled mHealth platform to support quality community-based primary maternal healthcare delivery at semi-urban, rural and deep rural clinics, based on end-user requirements in Southern Africa (Malawi, South Africa), East Africa (Kenya) & Horn of Africa (Ethiopia). This paper aims to share the co-design process applied to develop and validate Beta platform v1, and the implications this had on the design of subsequent iterations of the beta platform. The Beta platform v1 validation was undertaken with 36 participants from 11 healthcare clinics across Northern Ethiopia, Western Kenya, Southern Malawi and Eastern Cape, South Africa during November - December 2017, using a mix of ethnographic observation and semi-structured interviews. These findings have informed the co-design of the subsequent iterations of the mHealth4Afrika beta platform, which is being used in the participating clinics on a phased basis during Q3 - Q4 2018. This platform integrates Electronic Medical Records, Electronic Health Records, medical sensors, visualisation and automatically generate monthly health indicators, thus supporting better clinical care and decision making, and freeing up time for clinical care and continuous professional medical education, thus reducing mortality rates. The expected outcome is a multi-region proof of concept that can make a significant contribution in accelerating exploitation of mHealth across Africa to improve health outcomes and strengthen health systems.	CI1		

007	<p>Open data kit, a solution implementing a mobile health information system to enhance data management in public health</p>	<p>https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/6701738</p>	<p>A Reliable and accurate public health information system is essential for monitoring health and for evaluating and improving the delivery of health-care services and programmes. In Public health, decision-making is critically dependent on the timely availability of accurate and sound data. Open Data Kit (ODK) a free and open-source set of tools can be used by health organizations to author, field, and manage mobile data collection as a sustainable m-Health solution. m-Health encompasses health-related uses of telecommunication and multimedia technologies within health service delivery and public health systems in data collection and management to enhance data quality, reduce turn-around time and facilitate immediate feedback to health systems. This paper evaluates the implementation of ODK as an m-Health solution to enhance data management in public health</p>		<p>CE1</p> <p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema. Apresenta a validação de um sistema já implementado.</p>
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